

REPAIR OF CRACKED ALUMINUM AIRCRAFT STRUCTURE WITH GRAPHITE/EPOXY PATCHES

H. Leibovich, N. Sasson, A. Simon and A.K. Green
ISRAEL AIRCRAFT INDUSTRIES
Ben Gurion International Airport
70100 ISRAEL

ABSTRACT

The concept of repairing cracked aluminum aircraft structures with composite patches was investigated both analytically and experimentally. Coupon tests provided basic mechanical properties of composite patches manufactured using a repair procedure. A new surface treatment for bonding patches was developed and optimized. The damage repair process was substantiated by elements and beam testing. Crack growth predictions were made using analytical stress intensity factors for the patched structure, and excellent correlation was obtained between observed and predicted values.

Patches were very effective in reducing the crack growth rate. Cracks of patched element specimens which propagated to failure during random spectrum fatigue loading survived without failure for much longer lifetimes (approx. 3.5 times) under all tested environmental conditions. The process was then substantiated by repairing and testing a defective beam element.

Key words: composites, repair, graphite/epoxy composite, bonding, aircraft structure.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have been used for over twenty years to repair and structurally enhance metallic aircraft structures. Boron epoxy patches have been widely applied on military aircraft (Mirage, F111, C-130, C-141, etc.) and recently are being evaluated for civil aircraft. The general concept for repair of cracked metallic aircraft structures with composite patches has been investigated previously. The pioneering work of ARL, Australia, as reviewed in [1], describes the extensive development carried out on patching and structural analysis techniques using boron fiber reinforced patches, culminating in routine service use. Later developments have incorporated graphite fiber patching. Selective reinforcement of C-130 center wing boxes using boron fiber composite is described in [2]. Comparison of analytical and experimental crack growth behavior was investigated by Ratwani and Labor in [3].

The present work describes a new methodology for repairing cracked aluminum structures with graphite epoxy composite patches. Since the boron epoxy repair technology is limited to virtually flat surfaces, graphite epoxy repairs have been evaluated as the main repair option, to provide geometric flexibility for application to real structures.

The present work was performed in three main stages: Coupons, Elements and Beam. The coupon testing provided basic mechanical properties of composite material manufactured using

a repair procedure as well as surface treatment for bonding patches to aluminum. In the second stage, the damage repair process was substantiated by element testing. Crack growth predictions were made using analytical stress intensity factors for the patched structure. In the third stage, a pre-cracked aluminum beam was repaired using graphite epoxy composites and tested at room temperature.

2. COUPONS

2.1 Experimental

In the coupon stage, mechanical properties of graphite/epoxy laminates cured at 130°C and full vacuum (simulated repair conditions) were obtained. The prepreg used was Fiberite 7714 AC/70-3K-PW. A reduction was evident in both resin and fiber dominated properties, indicating the overall degradation in laminate quality resulting from the vacuum curing process. Results of the mechanical properties, which are summarized in Figure 1, provided a basis for design and analysis of structural repair patches under repair conditions.

2.2 Surface preparation

The surface preparation for bonding the aluminum to the composite was developed and optimized, based on Pasa Jell 105 treatment. Several techniques for applying Pasa Jell were compared. In addition, American Cyanamid BR 127 primer application and cure was adapted to repair conditions. Evaluation of the durability of these processes was carried out using the Bell Peel Test (wet and dry) using FM 73 film adhesive bonded under repair conditions.

3. ELEMENTS

3.1 Experimental

Unpatched and patched test specimens were prepared and tested to determine the effect of composite patches on the fatigue crack growth behavior of repaired parts. Figure 2 shows the test panel configuration.

Initial cracks in both types of test specimens were made by drilling a hole of $d=2.4$ mm at the center line of a 1.6 mm thick 2024-T81 aluminum panel. An elliptical notch was then cut around the hole to a total length of 12.7 mm. The specimens were then precracked on an "Instron" machine and crack length was monitored by crack propagation gauges up to 18 mm. Each specimen was loaded at constant cyclic loads in order to initiate a fatigue precrack. These cycles were applied at four stress levels in gradually decreasing amplitudes in order to eliminate any possible undesirable retardation effects.

The patched cracked panel was first prepared for bonding using the Pasa Jell surface treatment, and then primed with BR 127 primer. FM 73 film adhesive, a ply of style 120 fiberglass prepreg and eight plies ($\pm 45,0_3$)₂ of Fiberite 7714 AC/3K-70-PW graphite epoxy prepreg were co-cured together under full vacuum and 130°C on the precracked aluminum panel.

A total of twelve specimens were tested at three different conditions, RT, -55°C and 70°C plus 95%RH after preconditioning for two months at 60°C, 95%RH. The specimens were loaded by flight-by-flight type spectrum loads. A total of 12,720 load events of all types are assumed to occur during a period of 500 flight hours (FL.H.). A block of 500 FL.H. is equivalent to 1047 flights. Three types of flights were included: 812 Air-to-Air missions, 234 Air-to-Ground missions and 1 marker flight. The block of flights was repeated until failure of the specimen occurred, i.e. when the block of 1047 flights was over, another identical block of flights was started. The marker flight was applied at the end of each block (flight no. 1047).

Ultrasonic and modified Eddy-Current inspection were carried out before the test (after

manufacture of specimens and bonding of the graphite epoxy fabric patch) and then periodically during the test to detect possible debonding and crack growth.

Table 1 gives a summary of test results. Graphical comparison of crack growth propagation between different groups of specimens (according to type or environmental conditions) is shown in Figure 3.

Element test				
Specimen No. (Type)	Fatigue test			
	Preloading conditioning	Environmental conditions	Failure	
			Flight no.	Flight hour
1	None	R.T.	55490	26499
2		R.T.	53654	25623
3 (Patched)		R.T.	53895	25738
4	None	-54°C	54171	25870
5		-54°C	68054	32499
6 (Patched)		-54°C	56301	26887
7	60°C/95%R.H.	70°C/95%R.H.	42476	20285
8		70°C/95%R.H.	Fail.	at grip
9 (Patched)		70°C/95%R.H.	32320	15435
10	None	R.T.	16237	7754
11		R.T.	14786	7061
12 (Unpatched)		R.T.	16955	8097

Table 1. Element test results: unpatched and patched specimens.

3.2 Analysis

The analysis of a composite patch bonded to a cracked aluminum part as shown in Figure 2 was carried out using a finite element approach. The finite element analysis was used to determine the stress intensity factor K of a patched center crack panel, and then the stress intensity correction factor β . The presence of a bonded patch in the structure causes out of plane bending due to lack of symmetry induced by the patch. This bending causes an increase in the stress intensity factor which will increase as the crack length increases. The analysis of crack growth should take this phenomenon into consideration. In order to estimate the accuracy of the finite element method, analysis was performed first for the unpatched test specimen using the stress intensity factors given in the literature. After verification of the finite element method and the stress intensity factor calculation, analysis was performed for patched test specimens.

The strain energy release rate method is used here to derive the stress intensity factors K and

stress intensity correction factors β of the cracked plate. For linear elastic fracture mechanics, the stress intensity factor K is related to the strain energy release rate $\partial U/\partial a$ through the following equation:

$$K = \left[\frac{\partial U}{\partial a} \frac{E}{\alpha k t} \right]^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

where:

- | | | | |
|------------|--|-----|--------------------|
| U = | Total strain energy of finite element model | a = | Crack length |
| E = | Modulus of elasticity | t = | Plate thickness |
| α = | The number of crack tips contained in the finite element model (1/2 when modelling a symmetric half of a one crack tip configuration). | k = | 1 for plane stress |

The finite element analysis was used to derive the stress intensity factor K for the unpatched test specimen. The symmetric configuration of the test specimen was taken into account and only one quarter of a plate was modelled by plate elements. Each of the twenty Nastran subcases describes a different crack length and strain energy. The stress intensity factor K may be derived from the finite element solution of two successive crack lengths by the use of a finite difference approximation of Equation 1.

The stress intensity factor can also be written as:

$$K(a_i) = \left[\frac{\Delta U}{\Delta a} \frac{E}{\alpha k t} \right]^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

$$K(a_i) = \beta \sigma \sqrt{\pi a_i} \quad (3)$$

where:

- | | | | |
|--------------|----------------------|-------------------------|-------------------------------------|
| ΔU = | $U_i - U_{i-1}$ | $\frac{U_i}{a_i}$ = | Strain energy at crack length a_i |
| σ = | Remote stress | $\frac{a_i}{a_{i-1}}$ = | $(a_i + a_{i-1})/2$ |
| a_i = | Current crack length | a_{i-1} = | Previous crack length |

From Equation 3, the stress intensity correction factor can be determined for each two successive crack lengths by the following equation.

$$\beta = \frac{K(\bar{a}_i)}{\sigma \sqrt{\pi \bar{a}_i}} \quad (4)$$

In the same manner, the stress intensity correction factor β was calculated for all other cases. The exact solution for the stress intensity correction factor can be written as:

$$\beta = \sqrt{\sec \frac{\pi \bar{a}}{w}} \quad (5)$$

Where: w = Plate width

The β values obtained using the exact solution are in agreement with those from finite

element analysis as shown in Figure 4.

In addition, for the patched specimen, the adhesive film was modelled by solid elements and the composite patch was modelled by plate elements. The resulting stress intensity correction factor β is shown in Figure 5.

Computer software based on a closure retardation model was used to analyze the fatigue crack growth in order to determine structural life time. The β values obtained from Figure 4 are used to compute the stress intensity factor using the equation:

$$\Delta K = \beta \Delta \sigma \sqrt{\pi a} \quad (6)$$

The stress intensity range, ΔK , is computed from the growth rate equation. Next, the first order equation is integrated to find the new crack length. The fatigue crack growth analysis was carried out for the patched specimen. Comparison between predicted life time using analytical techniques and test results shows excellent correlation, as shown in Figure 6.

4. BEAM TEST

A defective aluminum beam with deliberately thin web walls was precracked and repaired using the procedures developed in the coupon and element stages. Special devices were used during the repair in order to assure good performance of the co-curing/bonding process. The repaired beam as shown in Figure 7 was loaded for four lifetimes and then tested for residual strength. The patches reduced the stress level by approximately 20% in relation to the unpatched beam.

Crack growth, debonding and delaminations were evaluated using the non-destructive procedures described in the element stage. No debonds or delaminations were observed during the fatigue loading testing.

5. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

- (a) A method for in-situ repair of geometrically complex aluminum structures using composite materials was developed.
- (b) The repair process was substantiated by element and beam fatigue testing.
- (c) Surface preparation of aluminum for bonding using the Pasa Jell method assured good durability, even under severe hot/wet conditions.
- (d) Patches are very effective in reducing crack growth rate.
- (e) An analytical model was developed for service repair design and life prediction.

References

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Figure 1. Comparison between vacuum and autoclave cure properties.

Figure 2. Geometry of element test specimens.(All dimensions in mm).

Figure 3. Crack growth propagation for different groups of test specimens.

Figure 4. Comparison between β from F.E.M and β from exact solution.

Figure 5. β from F.E.M for patched test specimen (RT conditions).

Figure 6. Comparison between predicted life time and test results (RT conditions).

Figure 7. Beam test specimen.